

Evidence in Action: Screening for Bipolar Disorder with the HCL-32 in $N = 6$ Adult Puerto Rican Female Outpatients with MDD

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ABSTRACT

It takes ~10 years to reach an accurate bipolar disorder (BD) diagnosis in community clinics, increasing risk of mortality and morbidity. This study aimed to identify clinical correlates of possible BD in outpatients with Major Depressive Disorder (MDD) to improve diagnostic accuracy in non-psychiatric settings. **Method:** For this exploratory, cross-sectional study, $n = 6$ adult female outpatients diagnosed with MDD were recruited by availability from a primary health clinic. HCL-32, YMRS, BDI-II, PHQ-9, FAST were used to screen for hypomania, depression and functional impairment. Clinical correlates were identified from the evidence and analyzed in the sample with nonparametric tests. **Results:** An almost 3-fold increase in depression severity was found in subjects with possible BD ($n = 2$ BD family history, 1 MDD FHx). Patients with BD family history had earlier illness onset, positive HCL-32 total and irritability/risk-taking scores, histories of alcohol or substance abuse and severe functional impairment. 4/6 participants had MDD family history, but the one with possible BD (irritability/risk-taking only) also had early illness onset and history of postpartum depression, both associated with BD. All possible BD participants had prior hospitalizations. **Conclusion:** HCL-32 effectively screened for possible BD in a small clinical sample, pointing to the usefulness of this measure as a screening intervention in non-psychiatric settings. Findings from this study support evidence-based clinical correlates on a “micro” level, supporting the need for concise, evidence-based screening interventions to identify BD in MDD patients.

KEYWORDS: major depressive disorder, bipolar disorder, mixed moods, early age of onset, HCL-32, BDI-II

ARTICLE DETAILS

Published On:
28 August 2025

Available on:
<https://ijmscr.org/>

INTRODUCTION

Bipolar Disorder (BD) is a highly heritable illness. First-degree relatives of BD patients have a 10-fold risk of developing bipolar depression (Smoller & Finn, 2003). Likewise, in a study with a sample size of 1,165 patients with bipolar disorder and 1,041 patients with unipolar depression, up to 41.2% of subjects with BD type I reported a family history of BD, while 18.5% of patients with unipolar depression reported family history of BD (Parker, Romano, Graham, & Ricciardi, 2018). Likewise, the prevalence of BD family history in BD-II corresponded to that of BD I. Because family history of BD is one of the most consistent risk factors for BD, it has increased relevance as a clinical marker for BD in subjects who initially present with unipolar depression.

However, not all potential BD patients have a reported family history of BD. In such cases, it is necessary to rely on other clinical correlates to differentiate potential BD-II from major depressive disorder (MDD), since many BD II patients often experience depression or mixed mood states as the primary mood disturbance. Besides early illness onset (< 25 years old), another well-established correlate of BD, increased receptiveness to rewarding experiences and *behavioral activation* is the next best predictor of BD (Boland, et al., 2016). For instance, an increasingly active pursuit of new experiences, a stronger drive to socialize, and engaging more compulsively in risk-taking behavior have all been recognized as features of hypomanic episodes. While positive interpretations of these drives generally underlie active or elated moods, they can just as well underlie

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irritable/risk-taking behavior. As the unsustainable level of activity of the elevated phase begins to wane, if not *physically exhaust* the BD system as recent allostatic load-neuroprogressive theory suggests, the pursuit of new experiences can transform into impulsive spending sprees and increased social-minded can transform into increasingly aggressive or hostile attitudes.

Like their BD-I counterparts, individuals with BD-II experience more sensitive behavioral activation systems. As such, symptoms such as significantly increased sleep and appetite, intrinsically rewarding in nature, have been associated with bipolar depression. Due to neuroprotective factors like increased DLPFC-amygdala coupling, however, BD-II patients are more likely to engage more effective emotion regulation strategies to dampen over-elevated moods but not survival-based stress responses like fear, which readily activate the sympathetic flight-or-fight system and thus agitation, irritability and risk-taking as part of the stress response.

While numerous quantitative studies with large sample sizes have endeavored to clarify bipolar differential correlates, few studies address this issue from a qualitative or mixed methods perspective. In other words, there is a well-supported body of evidence for the predictive power of certain BD correlates but the applicability of these findings on a smaller scale is not readily understood. How would a clinician “know” when to assess for bipolar disorder when the manic component is not that evident? A clinician well-versed in bipolar disorder might have no issue “knowing where to look”, so to speak, but a clinician from another field of expertise might not have the resources or availability of time to readily differentiate between mood disorder types. While this exploratory study primarily aimed to identify BD-II in MDD patients, it also aimed to assess the clinical character of mixed mood presentations through a case-comparison analysis of $n = 6$ female outpatients diagnosed with MDD, receiving treatment in a primary health clinic—a setting which is not primarily psychiatric in nature.

ASSESSING RISK-TAKING/IRRITABILITY AS MIXED MOOD DEPRESSIVE EPISODE

The *Hypomania Check List – 32* (HCL-32), a self-rated instrument created to assess history of (hypo)manic symptoms in patients with MDD (Angst, et al., 2005), has a “Risk-Taking/Irritability” subscale that *can accurately identify a significant history of hypomanic irritability symptoms with a cut-off point of 3* (Angst, et al., 2012). Irritability, like anxiety and agitation, is a symptom common to both bipolar and unipolar depression. As such, a higher threshold for BD diagnosis (4/7 DSM-5 hypomanic symptoms) has been recommended in cases of MDD with irritable mood only (Angst et al., 2012). Increased mood lability and mixed states while on antidepressants has also been found in depressed patients with an HCL-32 history of

irritable hypomania (*ibid*). Furthermore, increased activity/agitation, increased talkativeness and decreased need for sleep have been found in patients who answered positively to three mania gate questions based on DSM-IV diagnostic criterion A1: irritability, elevated mood and new or increased activity (*ibid*; p.5). Additionally, an increasing number of hypomanic symptoms correlated significantly with rates of functional impairment, outpatient treatment and hospitalizations. Thus, co-assessing daily functioning with a measure like the Functional Assessment Short Test (FAST), specifically developed to assess BD patients, can improve screening specificity.

The HCL-32 has good construct validity – which means that *any identified risk-taking/irritability symptoms likely correspond to the behavioral activation/reward-seeking sensitivities innervating BD*. As such, the HCL-32 was used in this study as the primary measure of hypomanic history.

Mixed Mood Depression. Regarding depression symptoms, some authors (Sasdehli, et al., 2013) have found a positive correlation between total HCL-32 scores and the Patient Health Questionnaire (PHQ-9) scores, suggesting that *subjects who reported more hypomanic symptoms also tended to experience more severe depression*. Arguably, the finding extends to the Beck Depression Inventory (BDI-II) since there is good convergent validity between PHQ-9 and BDI-II scores, particularly with MDD outpatients (Kung, et al., 2013). This is important to note, since BDI-II is the “gold standard” for depression assessment in mental health care, while the PHQ-9 tends to prevail in medical settings. *As such, if a clinician were to perform the proposed BD screening in a primary care setting, results from the PHQ-9 would be comparable to those of the BDI-II.*

In terms of depressed mood *per se*, a meta-analysis completed by Ratheesh et al. (2017) found that ~22.5% adults and adolescents with MDD followed for a mean length of 12-18 years developed BD. Greatest risk of transition was during first five years and was predicted by BD family history, earlier depression onset and presence of psychotic symptoms. Subthreshold hypomanic symptoms were also associated with MDD-to-BD transition. Early MDD onset age was, on average, 4.8 years earlier than those who did not develop BD. Interestingly, no association was found between MDD family history and BD onset. *Psychotic symptoms, child abuse and severe childhood trauma were generally associated with later BD onset*. Severity of depression, guilt and mood lability coexistent with MDD was associated with BD in a few studies. Suicidal ideation or attempts did not consistently predict transition, nor did chronicity of depression (>2 years), generalized anxiety disorder (GAD), substance abuse disorders or atypical features (i.e. hypersomnia-retarded depression).

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METHOD

Data Collection Phase

A cross-sectional study was developed to assess BD prevalence in a sample of adult Puerto Rican outpatients diagnosed with MDD. Sociodemographic variables were collected to define sample characteristics. Evidence-based clinical variables like BD family history, age of illness onset and illness chronicity were defined according to well-established parameters in the field. For instance, early illness onset has been defined as < 25 years old (Cerimele, Chwastiak, Chan, Harrison, & Unutzer, 2013) while later onset has been defined as > 40 years (Schurhoff et al., 2000). Likewise, illness chronicity for BD has been defined as > 10 years since initial diagnosis (Berk et al., 2017).

Sociodemographic and clinical data was obtained during a one-time, semi-structured assessment interview, where patient-rated (HCL-32, BDI-II, PHQ-9) and clinician-rated (YMRS, FAST) scales of hypomania, depression and functional assessment were administered to a sample of $n = 6$ adult Puerto Rican female outpatients diagnosed with Major Depressive Disorder (MDD), between the ages of 21-64, currently receiving psychiatric treatment at the Ponce Health Sciences University – Wellness Center (PHSU-WC), Intensive Outpatient Clinic (IOC). According to Yin (2009), an $n = 6$ is the maximum number of cases recommended for a comprehensive case-comparison analysis of a phenomenon, in this case, mixed mood depression as a possible marker of BD. The sample was obtained by convenience, recruited directly from the IOC waiting area after providing brief group psychoeducation about mental health. Initial exclusion criteria were: 1) Being unwilling to participate or unable to consent due to neurocognitive impairment (previously diagnosed or MMSE score < 23) or reading disability; 2) Having a diagnosis of schizophrenia or schizoaffective disorders; 3) Requiring psychiatric hospitalization at time of assessment; 4) Currently with febrile infection or receiving chemotherapy. ICD-10 diagnosis of MDD or BD was confirmed by accessing electronic medical records after the interview.

Instruments

Beck Depression Inventory – Second Edition (BDI-II). The BDI-II (Beck, Steer, & Brown, 1996) is a 21-item questionnaire developed to assess the severity of self-reported cognitive, behavioral, affective and neurovegetative depression symptoms within a timeframe of two weeks. Items are intended to reflect diagnostic criteria for Major Depressive Disorders (MDD) as described in the DSM-IV-TR (Steer, Ball, Ranieri, & Beck, 1999) Most individual items follow a Likert-type structure ranging from 0-3, mild to severe. However, items in which neurovegetative symptoms (sleep and appetite) are assessed, are subdivided into positive or negative classifications, i.e. “1a – I sleep more than usual” and “1b – I sleep less than usual”. Overall scores are summed

and classified by symptom severity, as mild, moderate or severe. A score of 29 or higher is indicative of severe depression.

Patient Health Questionnaire – 9 (PHQ-9). The PHQ-9 (Kroenke & Spitzer, 2002) is a nine-item instrument originally developed to screen for depression in primary care settings (Beard, Hsu, Rifkin, Busch, & Bjorgvinsson, 2016). Scores range from 0 to 27, and scores greater than 10 have a sensitivity and specificity of 88% (Kroenke, Spitzer, & Williams, 2001). While the PHQ-9 is mainly used in medical settings, the instrument has been recently validated for psychiatric samples as a measure of severity (Beard et al., 2016), with good internal consistency ($\alpha = .87$). A cut-off score of 13 is recommended for psychiatric samples as it affords greater specificity of MDD symptoms (Sensitivity = .83, Specificity = .72) in a population with higher rates of comorbidity, illness severity and chronicity. The PHQ-9 has also shown good convergent validity with other measures of depression, such as the Beck Depression Inventory – Second Edition (BDI-II). Results from retrospective study ($n = 625$) by Kung, Alarcon, Williams, Poppe, Moore, & Frye (2013) indicate a strong correlation exists between PHQ-9 scores and BDI-II scores, especially in outpatients with MDD.

Hypomania Check List – 32 (HCL-32). The HCL-32 (Angst et al., 2005) is a 32-item questionnaire designed to assess history of mania or hypomania in patients diagnosed with MDD. Participants are asked to remember a time when they experienced a “high” state and to respond “yes” or “no” to behaviors, thoughts and emotions they experienced during such a state. The total score is the number of questions answered “yes”. With a sensitivity of 80% and a specificity of 51%, a total score of 14 or more is considered the most balanced cutoff point for clinically significant bipolar symptoms (Angst et al., 2005; Vieta et al., 2007). However, many research efforts have emerged to assess the psychometric properties of higher – or lower – cutoff points. One particular study conducted with a Taiwanese sample of medicated outpatients with MDD (Chou, et al., 2012) to assess the validity of the HCL-32 and the Mood Disorder Questionnaire (MDQ) found that *a total cutoff score of 7 had the best combination of sensitivity (100%) and specificity (46.2%)*. Another study with 199 adult outpatients diagnosed with mood disorders ($n = 39$ MDD) found that a total cutoff score of 9 had a sensitivity of 91% and a specificity of 46% (Wu, Angst, Ou, Chen, & Lu, 2008). On the other end of the cut-off spectrum, Camacho et al. (2017) found that a total score of 17 provided the best balance in sensitivity (80.8%) and specificity (23.9%) when discriminating BD from MDD and other psychiatric disorders.

The *irritable/risk-taking dimension* of the HCL-32 has been found to be more predictive of BD among non-clinical populations than the active/elated dimension, regardless of subtype (Lee et al., 2016) and has been known to discriminate between MDD and BD subjects with a cut-off

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score of 3 (Angst et al., 2005). Thus, while HCL-32 is a valid and reliable assessment tool for MDD-BD discrimination, a factorial approach can improve its moderate specificity. Furthermore, the powerful sensitivity of the Risk-Taking/Irritability subscale can improve the identification of true BD positives—useful when the main objective is to quickly and effectively identify a population highly burdened by suicidality risk. To this end, this study integrates Irritability/Risk-Taking scoring of the HCL-32 and a total cut-off score of 7 for maximum sensitivity and moderate specificity.

Young Mania Rating Scale (YMRS). The YMRS (Young, Biggs, Ziegler, & Meyer, 1978) is an 11-item clinician-rated scale to measure presence and severity of manic symptoms. This instrument is frequently used in research and clinical practice. Scores are obtained from observations made by the clinician during a 15 – 30-minute interview and by patient self-report of symptoms experienced in the past 48 hours. Areas assessed by the YMRS include: 1) Elevated mood; 2) Increased motor activity-energy; 3) Sexual interest; 4) Sleep; 5) Irritability; 6) Speech (Rate and Amount); 7) Language thought disorder; 8) Content; 9) Disruptive-aggressive behavior; 10) Appearance; 11) Insight. The scale does not include depressive symptoms. While most item severity scores range from 0 to 4, scores for items 5 (Irritability), 6 (Speech), 8 (Thought Content), and 9 (Disruptive-aggressive behavior) are doubled to compensate for lack of collaboration in subjects who are severely manic. A total score of ≤ 6 indicates euthymia or remission of symptoms; a total score of ≥ 12 suggests hypomanic symptoms, while a total score of ≥ 20 suggests severe manic symptoms (Colom, et al., 2002). The YMRS has been adapted into Spanish by Colom et al. (2002) with good internal and external validity ($p < .001$), a reliability index of 0.88 (high internal consistency) and good test-retest reliability (0.76).

Functional Assessment Short Test (FAST). The FAST (Rosa, et al., 2007) is a 24-item, clinician-rated questionnaire designed to assess specific psychosocial impairments experienced by patients with BD. The items are classified in six domains of functioning: 1) Autonomy, 2) Occupational Functioning, 3) Cognitive Functioning, 4) Finance, 5) Interpersonal Relationships, 6) Leisure. Functionality is assessed within a 15-day timeframe (Rosa et

al., 2007). Items are rated using a 4-point scale in which 0=no difficulty, 1=mild difficulty, 2=moderate difficulty, 3=severe difficulty. Functional difficulty is mainly assessed by the degree of assistance required during a task and is proportional to the global score obtained on the FAST. With a Cronbach's alpha of 0.909, the FAST has strong internal consistency and concurrent validity with Global Assessment Functioning (GAF) scores (Rosa et al., 2007). Meaningful cut-off points have been found for mild (12-20), moderate (21-40) and severe (>40) functional impairment (Bonnin et al., 2018).

Sociodemographic and Clinical History Questionnaire. A 14-item semi-structured interview guide developed by the author to collect sociodemographic data and relevant medical or psychiatric history.

Data Analysis Plan

Sociodemographic and clinical data were collected and analyzed using a mixed methods approach. Quantitative data were extracted and coded into a database for statistical analysis using Jamovi v.0.9.5.12, an open-source, R-based statistics program (<http://www.jamovi.org>). Descriptive statistics and non-parametric tests were performed to understand relevant associations and scoring patterns in a small sample.

Results from quantitative analyses were used to contextualize a series of brief case histories through Yin's case-comparison method. Sociodemographic and clinical history was triangulated with evidence-based findings and relevant quantitative findings from the current study to assess clinical pattern relevance to possible BD presentations.

RESULTS

General Sample Characteristics

Sociodemographic and clinical data was collected from $n=6$ adult Puerto Rican female outpatients at a primary health clinic. Two (2/6) participants reported a positive BD family history while the remaining four (4/6) reported positive MDD family history. Descriptive analysis of age and clinical correlates revealed bimodal distribution for age, age of illness onset, chronicity, HCL-32 Irritability/Risk-Taking scores and BDI-II total scores (Table 1). As such, median and interquartile range (IQR) was used as a proxy for mean and standard deviation.

Table 1. Whole-Sample Measures of Central Tendency for Clinical Correlates

	Age	Age of Onset	Illness Years	HCL-32 Total	HCL-32 I/R-T*	FAST	PHQ9 Total	BDI-II Total	YMRS
Mis.¹	0	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0
Mdn	49.5	25	22	5	3	38.0	20.5	33.0	5.00
Mode	40.0 ^a	15.0 ^a	3.00 ^a	5.00	0.00 ^a	35.0	27.0	10.0 ^a	2.00

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Table 1. Whole-Sample Measures of Central Tendency for Clinical Correlates

	Age	Age of Onset	Illness Years	HCL-32 Total	HCL-32 I/R-T*	FAST	PHQ9 Total	BDI-II Total	YMRS
IQR	15.8	24.0	6.00	4.00	4.00	7.25	15.3	26.5	5.50
Min.	40	15	3	4	0	35	8	10	2
Max.	62	56	30	13	6	54	27	52	11

^a More than one mode exists, only the first is reported. * The Active/Elated dimension of the HCL-32 was not included due to inconsistent findings regarding its stand-alone predictive value. Per Angst et al., an Irritability/Risk-Taking score of > 3 is clinically significant. ¹ One participant did not report age of illness onset nor complete the HCL-32, so these clinical variables were analyzed with an n=5.

Table 2. Kruskal-Wallis Clinical Correlates According to Early vs. Late Onset Type

	χ^2	df	p	ϵ^2
Psychiatric Hospitalizations	4.00	1	0.046*	1.000
BDI-II Total	3.00	1	0.083	0.750
Loss of Pleasure	1.78	1	0.182	0.444
Irritability	2.31	1	0.128	0.579
BDI-II Severity¹	3.75	1	0.053*	0.938
PHQ-9 Total	3.75	1	0.053*	0.938
FAST	3.16	1	0.076	0.789
HCL-32 I/R-T	4.00	1	0.046*	1.000
YMRS	1.33	1	0.248	0.333
Mood Disorder Family History (BD or MDD)²	1.78	1	0.182	0.444

¹ While no significant differences were found between BDI-II total score medians, BDI-II severity scores, coded as an ordinal variable pointing to presence/absence of BDI-II score severity, did produce significant differences between onset groups, with early onset individuals showing greater severity of depression. *Statistically significant differences at the .05 level. ² Was not significant for either MDD or BD family.

Sociodemographic and Clinical History and Age of Illness Onset

Median age for overall sample was 49.5 years (IQR = 15.8; minimum = 40 y, maximum = 62 y). Three (3/6) participants had some college education. Regarding civil

status, three participants were married, two were divorced and one was single. All reported inactive work status. Regarding clinical history, all had an ICD-10 diagnosis of MDD. Most (4/6) had MDD specified as severe, without psychotic features. However, one participant had psychotic features, while another had unspecified severity. Comorbid psychiatric diagnoses were generalized anxiety disorder ($n = 2$), panic attacks ($n = 1$) and insomnia ($n = 1$). All participants had some history of substance use: 4/6 reported past or current smoking history, 1/6 reported past cannabis use, 1/6 reported history of alcohol abuse. Three participants reported past psychiatric hospitalizations for aggression, postpartum depression, and suicidality (Table 3).

Table 3. Sociodemographic and Clinical Characteristics of n = 6 Female MDD

Sample Characteristics	N=6 Puerto Rican female outpatients with MDD					
	BDFH001	MDFH002	MDFH003	MDFH004	MDFH005	MDFH006
<i>Age</i>	42y	40y	54y	60y	62y	45y

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<i>Education</i>	High School	A.S. or Some College	A.S. or Some College	Middle School	A.S. or Some College	High School
<i>Relationship Status</i>	Divorced	Married	Married	Single	Divorced	Married
<i>ICD-10 MDD</i>	Single episode, unspecified	Severe, without psychotic features	Severe, without psychotic features	Severe, with psychotic features	Single episode, severe, without psychotic features	Recurrent, severe, without psychotic features
<i>Family History Onset</i>	BD Early (20y)	MDD Early (25y)	MDD Missing	MDD Late (56y)	MDD Late (44y)	BD Early (15y)
<i>Comorbid Psychiatric Trauma hx./Significant Life Events</i>	None	Panic attacks	PTSD	None	GAD	GAD, Insomnia
<i>Psychiatric Hospitalizations</i>	Past suicide attempt	Postpartum Depression	PTSD; Loss of sister (1 month ago)	Hx. Psychotic episodes	Uterine Cancer, Hysterectomy	Loss of job (1 year ago)
<i>Alcohol/Sub Medication</i>	Unspecified	N=1 Partial	None reported	None reported	None reported	N=1 Partial (Aggression)
	Past Cannabis	None reported	None reported	Heavy smoking	None reported	Past alcohol abuse
	SSRI, Tri-cyclic (Flexeril)	SNRI, Antipsychotic (Quetiapine)	SSRI, Tri-cyclic (Flexeril), Ambien 10mg	SSRI, Tri-cyclic	SSRI, Tri-cyclic	SSRI

Note: All participants were unemployed at time of the study.

Age of Illness Onset. Lowest age of illness onset overall ($n = 5$, 1 missing) was 15 years old, while the latest age of onset was 56 years ($mdn = 25y$, $IQR=24.0$). A Kruskal-Wallis non-parametric analysis of variance was conducted to assess the possibility of bimodality pointing to early vs. late illness onset (Table 2). Significant differences were found between early and late onset groups for HCL-32 Irritability Risk-Taking scores ($H[1] = 4.00$, $p = 0.046$, $\epsilon^2 = 1.00$) and psychiatric hospitalizations ($H[1] = 4.00$, $p = 0.046$, $\epsilon^2 = 1.00$), as well as PHQ-9 total scores and BDI-II severity status ($H [1] = 3.75$, $p = 0.053$, $\epsilon^2 = 0.938$), which survived post-hoc Dwass-Steel-Critchlow-Fligner (DSCF) pairwise comparisons.

Hypomania. The median for the clinician-rated YMRS ($mdn = 5$, $IQR = 5.50$) suggested that the sample was mostly non-hypomanic at time of assessment. HCL-32 scores were calculated for $n = 5$ due to missing data ($n = 1$). The overall median total score was 5 ($IQR = 4.00$), with a maximum score of 13. Meanwhile, the overall median for HCL-32 Irritability/Risk-Taking scores was 3 ($IQR = 4.00$; maximum = 6), considered clinically significant. A Kruskal-Wallis non-parametric one-way ANOVA found significant differences in HCL-32 Risk-Taking/Irritability scores between early or late onset groups ($H [1] = 4.00$, $p = 0.046$, $\epsilon^2 = 1.00$; Figure 1) but not for HCL-32 total scores (Table 2).

Figure 1. Histogram of HCL-32 Risk-Taking/Irritability scores by age of onset ($n=5$, 1 missing; 2 BD family history, 3 MDD FHx). Those with early onset ($n=3$) scored ≥ 3 ; late onset ($n=2$) scored < 3 .

Functional Assessment. The overall sample ($n = 6$) experienced moderate to severe difficulties in daily functioning (FAST mdn score = 38, IQR = 7.25). The minimum FAST score obtained was 35 (moderate functional impairment), while the highest was 54 (severe functional impairment). A Kruskal-Wallis non-parametric ANOVA did not find significant differences in FAST scores between early or late onset groups (Table 2).

Depression. Both PHQ-9 and BDI-II total scores confirmed current depression in the sample (PHQ-9 total mdn = 20.5, IQR = 15.3; BDI-II total mdn = 33, IQR = 26.5). One participant scored below the PHQ-9 for psychiatric samples (< 13) but within the mild depression range in the BDI-II (BDI-II total score = 16). However, a Friedman repeated measures ANOVA (non-parametric) found no significant differences between PHQ-9 and BDI-II scores for the whole sample (PHQ-9 Total - BDI-II Total, 1.838, 0.074). The maximum PHQ-9 score ($n = 27$) was reported by 3/6 participants.

A Kruskal-Wallis non-parametric one-way ANOVA did not find significant differences in BDI-II total scores between early-late onset groups ($H[1] = 3.00$, $p = 0.083$) but did find significant differences in BDI-II severe scores

specifically ($H[1] = 3.75$, $p = 0.053$, $\epsilon^2 = 0.938$) and in PHQ-9 scores ($H[1] = 3.75$, $p = 0.053$, $\epsilon^2 = 0.938$).

Clinical Correlates Stratified by Mood Disorder Family History

To fully assess the distribution pattern of clinical correlates, descriptive statistics were stratified by BD or MDD family history (Table 4). One participant with MDD family history did not report age of illness onset nor complete the HCL-32, so central tendency for those variables was calculated with a sample $n = 5$. A bimodal tendency resurfaced, likely due to differences in illness onset (Table 1 and 2). For instance, an *earlier illness onset* was observed in the BD family history sample (mdn = 17.5y, IQR = 2.50; min = 15y, max = 20y) vs MDD family history (mdn = 44y, IQR = 15.5; min = 25y, max = 56y). However, Kruskal-Wallis non-parametric one-way ANOVA comparing age of illness onset by family history group was not statistically significant ($H[1] = 3.00$, $p = 0.083$). Similarly, *number of psychiatric hospitalizations* significantly differed between early-late onset groups according to the Kruskal-Wallis nonparametric one-way ANOVA ($H[1] = 4.00$, $p = 0.046$, $\epsilon^2 = 1.00$) but not between family history types, suggesting that these

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differences were more likely mediated by age of illness onset (Table 2).

Table 4. Clinical Correlates Stratified by Mood Disorder Family History

	Fx	Age	Age of Onset ¹	# of Yrs. ¹	# Ill	HCL-32 Total ¹	HCL-32 I/R-T ¹	FAST	PHQ9 Total	BDI-II Total	YMRS
Mdn	MD	57.0	44	18	5	1	36.0	12.5	20.5	2.50	
	BD	43.5	17.5	26.0	11.0	5.50	49.0	27.0	49.0	9.50	
Mod	MD	40.0 ^a	25.0 ^a	3.00 ^a	5.00	0.00 ^a	35.0	8.00 ^a	10.0 ^a	2.00	
	BD	42.0 ^a	15.0 ^a	22.0 ^a	9.00 ^a	5.00 ^a	44.0 ^a	27.0	46.0 ^a	8.00 ^a	
IQR	MD	10.0	15.5	10.5	0.500	1.50	2.50	7.00	14.5	2.00	
	BD	1.50	2.50	4.00	2.00	0.500	5.00	0.00	3.00	1.50	
Min.	MD	40	25	3	4	0	35	8	10	2	
	BD	42	15	22	9	5	44	27	46	8	
Max.	MD	62	56	24	5	3	39	27	41	7	
	BD	45	20	30	13	6	54	27	52	11	

^a More than one mode exists, only the first is reported. Per Angst et al., an Irritability/Risk-Taking score of > 3 is clinically significant. ¹One participant did not report age of illness onset nor complete the HCL-32, so these clinical variables were analyzed with an n=5. None of these variables achieved statistical significance in a Kruskal-Wallis nonparametric ANOVA by family history type (Table 5).

Age of Illness Onset (MDD vs BD family history). The lowest age of illness onset, reported by a participant with BD family history, was 15 y/o, while the latest age of onset, reported by a participant with MDD family history, was 56 y/o (*n* = 5 overall *mdn* = 25y, *IQR* = 24.0). Meanwhile, the maximum reported age of onset for BD family history was 20 years old—still within the early illness onset range (< 25 years). In contrast, the median age of onset for the MDD family history group (*n* = 4) was 44 years old (*IQR*=15.5y), classifiable as late onset (> 40 years).

Figure 2. A histogram of age of onset stratified by mood disorder family history (n=5, 1 missing; 2 BD family history, 3 MDD FHx). Two participants with MDD family history were classifiable as late onset (> 40 years old), while another had an early onset (n=25y).

Hypomania (MDD vs BD family history).

Stratified by family history, a trend was observed for higher YMRS scores in the BD family history sample ($n = 2$, $mdn = 9.50$, $IQR = 1.50$) vs MDD family history ($n = 4$, $mdn = 2.50$, $IQR = 2.00$; Figure 3). However, these differences did not reach statistical significance in a Kruskal-Wallis nonparametric one-way ANOVA ($H[1] = 3.53$, $p = 0.060$). Likewise, marked differences in HCL-32 total score medians were observed between BD-MDD family history groups (BD

$n = 2$, $mdn = 11.0$, $IQR = 2.00$; MDD $n = 3$, $mdn = 5.0$, $IQR = 0.500$). However, these did not reach statistical significance in the Kruskal-Wallis nonparametric one-way ANOVA ($H[1] = 3.16$, $p = 0.076$). A similar trend was observed for HCL-32 Irritability/Risk-Taking scores (BD $n = 2$, $mdn = 5.50$, $IQR = 0.050$; MDD $n = 3$, $mdn = 1.00$, $IQR = 1.50$), which did not reach statistical significance in the Kruskal-Wallis ($H[1] = 3.00$, $p = 0.083$).

Figure 3. Histogram of HCL-32 Irritability/Risk-Taking scores visualized by mood disorder family history. Overall, scores ranged from 0 to 6 in a sample of $n = 5$ (1 missing). MDD range was 0-3; for BD was 5-6.

Functional Assessment. A 13-point difference in FAST score medians was observed between BD ($n = 2$, $mdn = 49.0$, $IQR = 5.00$) and MDD family history ($n = 3$, $mdn = 36$, $IQR = 2.50$). This difference did not reach statistical significance in the Kruskal Wallis test (BD-MDD Fam Hx.

FAST, $H[1] = 3.53$, $p = 0.060$). However, both positive BD family history participants scored in the severe functional impairment range, while all MDD family history participants scored in the moderate range (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Histogram of FAST scores stratified by mood disorder family history (n = 2 BD, 4 MDD). Range of FAST scores for MDD = 35-39 (Moderate). Range of FAST for BD = 44-54 (Severe).

Depression. An almost 3-fold increase in BDI-II scores was observed in participants with positive BD family history ($n = 2$ mdn = 49.0, IQR = 3.0; $n = 4$ MDD mdn = 20.5, IQR = 14.5; Figure 4). However, these differences did not achieve significance in the Kruskal-Wallis nonparametric ANOVA for the BDI-II (BD-MDD Fam Hx. BDI-II, $H[1] = 3.43$, $p = 0.064$) nor for the PHQ-9 (BD-MDD Fam Hx. PHQ-9, $H[1] = 2.18$, $p = 0.064$). Similarly, no significant differences in number of psychiatric hospitalizations were found between BD-MDD family history groups, despite 2/3 hospitalizations being reported by the BD family history group (Table 5).

Loss of Pleasure and Irritability. Because loss of pleasure and irritability are associated with mixed moods, corresponding item scores from the BDI-II (#4 and #17, respectively) were analyzed through a Kruskal-Wallis test by family history type, which found significant differences (BD-MDD Fam Hx. Loss of Pleasure, $H(1) = 4.00$, $p = 0.46$, $\epsilon^2 = 0.80$; BD-MDD FamHx. Irritability, $H(1) = 4.00$, $p = 0.46$, $\epsilon^2 = 0.80$; Table 5).

Figure 5. Histogram of BDI-II total scores stratified by mood disorder family history ($n=6$). Both positive BD family history participants had the highest scores, pointing to greater severity of depression.

Table 5. Kruskal-Wallis One-Way ANOVA of Clinical Correlates by Family History

	χ^2	df	p	ϵ^2
Age of Onset	3.00	1	0.083	0.750
YMRS	3.53	1	0.060	0.706
HCL-32 Total	3.16	1	0.076	0.789
HCL-32 I/R-T	3.00	1	0.083	0.750
FAST	3.53	1	0.060	0.706
PHQ9 Total	2.18	1	0.140	0.435
BDI-II Total	3.43	1	0.064	0.686
Loss of Pleasure	4.00	1	0.046*	0.800
Irritability	4.00	1	0.046*	0.800
Psychiatric Hospitalizations	2.50	1	0.114	0.500

* Both loss of pleasure and irritability BDI-II item scores had significant differences across family history.

Case Summaries and Possible Outcomes

Results from quantitative analyses were used to determine possible BD status in a sample of $n = 3/6$ participants based on family history ($n = 2$ BD, 1 MDD). Cases were chosen for

their significant HCL-32 Risk-Taking/Irritability scores (> 3), early onset and BDI-II severity scores. Table 3 has a summary of sociodemographic characteristics.

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Case BDFH01

Participant BDFH01 was a 42-year-old Puerto Rican female, divorced, with a positive family history of BD. She had a current ICD-10 diagnosis of MDD, single episode, of unspecified severity and was receiving a tri-cyclic SSRI (Flexeril) for her symptoms. BDFH01 reported a history of early illness onset, with first depression episode at 20 years old (illness chronicity *n* = 22 years). She also reported a significant history of suicidality, with one (*n* = 1) previous attempt for which she was hospitalized. She also reported a history of cannabis use and nicotine smoking.

Mood Symptoms

BDFH01 reported feeling “much worse than usual” on the HCL-32. Congruently, her total BDI-II scores (*n* = 52) reflected severe depression in the past week. She reported sleeping somewhat less than usual (insomnia), feeling too tired to do “a lot of things” (fatigue), not having enough energy for anything, and having a significantly decreased appetite—“much less than before”. On the HCL-32, BDFH01 reported her activity levels as “generally more active than others”. She was instructed to remember a time in her life when she experienced an elevated mood and to describe how she felt then, regardless of current state. BDFH01 described her elevated mood as predominantly irritable/risk-taking, feeling more easily distracted, impatient and irritable, as if she was draining or irritating others. She also reported a tendency to start fights, drive faster and more carelessly. Regarding past elated mood, BDFH01 reported a history of increased sexual desire or activity, thinking faster, joking more often and engaging with wordplay. HCL-32 total scores (*n* = 8) point to possible BD, while Risk-Taking/Irritability scores (*n* = 5) suggest significant history of bipolar depression. A score of 11 on the clinician-rated YMRS point to current subclinical hypomanic symptoms.

Social and Daily Functioning

Patient BDFH01 reported significant difficulties in social and daily functioning (FAST total score = 44, Severe). Her greatest difficulties were mostly in interpersonal functioning: participating in social activities, getting along with close friends and family, and sustaining satisfactory romantic or sexual relationships. She also had the most trouble completing chores around the house and learning new information.

Case BDFH06

BDFH06 was a 45-year-old female, married, with a positive family history of BD. She had an ICD-10 diagnosis of MDD, recurrent, severe, without psychotic features, with co-occurring generalized anxiety disorder (GAD), insomnia, and history of trauma (exposure to disaster). She also had a prior history of alcohol abuse and one partial hospitalization for aggressive behavior. BDFH06 was receiving an SSRI for her mood symptoms. She reported a history of early

depression onset at 15 years old (illness chronicity *n* = 30 years).

Mood Symptoms

Participant BDFH06 reported feeling “much worse than usual” on the HCL-32. She considered her activity levels as “generally more active than others” despite current mood. Her total BDI-II scores (*n* = 46) reflected severe depression in the past week. She reported sleeping “a lot more” than usual (hypersomnia), feeling too tired to do “most things” (fatigue), not having enough energy for anything (decreased energy), and having an appetite “somewhat greater than usual” (hyperphagia).

When completing HCL-32, BDFH06 was instructed to remember a time in her life when she experienced an elevated mood and to describe how she felt then, regardless of current state. Patient described her elevated mood as predominantly irritable/risk-taking: feeling more distractible, with a tendency to overspend, take more risks, start more fights, and feeling as if she was draining or irritating others. Regarding past elated moods, BDFH06 reported thinking faster, joking more often, feeling more creative, often engaging in wordplay, starting new projects or pursuing novel experiences. HCL-32 total scores (*n* = 11) point to possible BD. Risk-Taking/Irritability scores (*n* = 6) point to significant history of bipolar depression. A score of 8 on the clinician-rated YMRS suggests that BDFH06 had residual hypomanic symptoms at the time of the interview.

Social and Daily Functioning

Patient BDFH06 reported significant difficulties in social and daily functioning (FAST total score = 54, Severe). Her autonomy was seemingly the most affected, reporting much difficulty completing house chores, living alone, buying groceries or taking care of herself. BDFH06 also reported much difficulty finding work, managing work duties and completing tasks as quickly as needed. Relatedly, BDFH06 reported losing a job one year prior as a recent and significant event. In the cognitive domain, BDFH06 reported trouble completing mental arithmetic and adequately solving a problem. In the finance domain, BDFH06 reported difficulty managing own finances and making balanced purchases. In the interpersonal domain, B6 reported difficulty maintaining friendships, participating in social activities and getting along with others. She also noted difficulties engaging in pastime activities like sports, exercise or hobbies.

Case MDFH02

Participant was a 40-year-old female, married, with a negative family history of BD (but positive for MDD). She had an ICD-10 diagnosis of MDD, severe, without psychotic features and co-occurring panic attacks. MDFH02 had no reported history of alcohol or substance abuse. However, she had a significant history of postpartum depression for which she was hospitalized. She reported early onset at 25 years old

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(illness chronicity = 24 years). MDFH2 was currently receiving an SNRI and Quetiapine, an antipsychotic, as part of her treatment plan.

Mood Symptoms

MD2 reported feeling “slightly worse than usual” on the HCL-32. She considered her activity levels as “generally more active than others”, regardless of current mood. Her total BDI-II scores ($n = 46$) reflected severe depression in the past week. She reported sleeping somewhat less than usual (insomnia), feeling too tired to do “most things” (fatigue) and not having enough energy “to do very much”. Conversely, she reported “craving food all the time” (hyperphagia).

When completing HCL-32, MDFH02 was instructed to remember a time in her life when she experienced an elevated mood and to describe how she felt then, regardless of current state. Participant described her past elevated moods as predominantly irritable/risk-taking, feeling more distractible and impatient or as if she was draining or irritating others. Regarding history of elation, MDFH02 reported thinking faster during periods of increased activity. HCL-32 total scores ($n = 4$) did not meet the threshold for possible BD. However, Risk-Taking/Irritability scores ($n = 3$) point to possible bipolar depression. Clinician-rated YMRS score ($n = 3$) were not significant for hypomania.

Social and Daily Functioning

Patient MDFH02 reported moderate difficulties in social and daily functioning (FAST total score = 39). According to FAST responses, her finances were the most affected. MDFH02 reported much difficulty managing own budget and making balanced purchases. She also reported significant difficulty in the laboring domain, i.e. earning proportionate to the role occupied and meeting company expectations. In the interpersonal domain, MDFH02 reported trouble getting along with close family and friends. Regarding autonomy, MDFH02 also reported difficulty taking care of herself.

DISCUSSION

The present study analyzed evidence-based clinical correlates of bipolar disorder in a sample of $n = 6$ adult Puerto Rican female outpatients diagnosed with MDD (age range = 40 – 62 years old). All women were receiving treatment at a primary health clinic, which included psychiatric services, but was not a specialized mental health care setting, possibly limiting the availability of interventions specific to BD. All except one ($n = 1$ SNRI, 1 antipsychotic) were receiving treatment with SSRI and tri-cyclics. Only one patient had MDD with psychotic features.

Possible BD ($n = 3/6$). Of the six participants tested for past hypomanic symptoms, 3/6 reported positive BD Risk-Taking/Irritability symptoms. Two of these women (MDFH02) also had BD family histories—one of the strongest predictors of BD per the literature. One of these

participants did not have a family history of BD, but did report a family history of MDD, as did the remaining three participants. However, unlike the other 3/4 MDD family history participants, MDFH02 reported an early onset (25 years old), as did the 2/6 participants with positive BD family history, which aligns with evidence-based reports of early onset potentially leading to more severe illness course, if not outright transition into full BD (i.e. Schurhoff et al., 2000).

Bimodal Distribution, Age of Onset and Mood Disorder Family History. Initial analysis of whole-sample descriptives for this sample found a bimodal distribution for age, age of onset, chronicity or number of illness years, HCL-32 Irritability/Risk-Taking, and BDI-II scores (Table 1). Results from two Kruskal-Wallis nonparametric one-way ANOVAs (Table 2 and Table 5) suggested that these differences were more likely to be mediated by early or late onset rather than family history type, which supports evidence for the importance of age of onset, but was surprising in the context of the predictive value of BD family history. One possible explanation is the diagnostic course of BD: it takes approximately 10 years to reach an accurate diagnosis, and many patients might neither receive nor seek treatment at all. Poor treatment adherence is one of the bigger treatment issues with BD patients.

Depression Severity, BDI-II and PHQ-9. BDI-II severity and PHQ-9 scores significantly differed between early and late onset groups to a comparable degree (Table 2). The similar effectiveness of both measures ($H[1] = 3.75$, $p = 0.053$, $\epsilon^2 = 0.938$) may reflect the convergent validity of both measures as evidenced in the literature, but no significant differences were found in BDI-II total scores between both groups, suggesting that severity itself is the relevant marker. Indeed, more severe depression outcomes have been found to be associated with early illness onset, which makes sense: an earlier illness onset produces more opportunities for episodic recurrence and thus, earlier functional decline.

HCL-32 I/R-T by Onset vs Family History. Significant differences in HCL-32 Risk-Taking/Irritability scores were also found between early-late onset groups. Relevantly, this difference was not found when the sample was grouped according to mood family history, suggesting that age of onset is a more reliable predictor of hypomanic history than family history of BD—at least, in small clinical samples. However, because BD family history is nevertheless a relevant marker of heritability, the “loss of pleasure” item of the BDI-II was assessed as a proxy for reward sensitivity in subjects with potential BD—potentially heritable due to strong neuroanatomic correlates in patients with the condition. While significant differences in “loss of pleasure” were not found in early-late onset groups ($H[1] = 1.78$, $p = 0.182$), they did emerge in the sample when grouped by family history ($H[1] = 3.00$, $p = 0.046$, $\epsilon^2 = 0.80$). Both

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statistical significance of the Kruskal-Wallis test and the large effect size support the idea of reward/BAS sensitivity as a heritable component in patients at risk for BD.

Because one participant ($n = 1$ MDD family history) did not complete the HCL-32, nonparametric analyses with this measure were completed with an $n = 5$, which could be considered a limitation of the study. However, this participant completed the BDI-II, so the “irritability” item from the BDI-II was analyzed as an additional measure of irritability, if not a proxy for irritability/risk-taking, in patients with MDD. While no significant differences were found in level of irritability between early-late onset groups, significant differences—comparable to those of “loss of pleasure”—emerged when subjects were grouped by family history. This outcome raises the question of whether significant differences in HCL-32 Irritability/Risk-Taking scores would have emerged between BD-MDD family history groups if the subject had completed the HCL-32. However, neither loss of pleasure nor irritability differences reached statistical differences in age of onset groups, suggesting that both are more closely related to family history as markers of heritability.

Possible BD with BD or MDD History. Regarding the case studies themselves, those who reported clinically significant HCL-32 Irritability/Risk-Taking scores were analyzed for potential BD. Both participants with BD family histories seemed to follow a course of illness typical of BD: both had early illness onset and, notably, both had the only “severe” functional impairment ratings as scored by the FAST, a measure developed specifically to assess functional impairment in patients with BD. Both participants accounted for 2/3 psychiatric hospitalizations reported by the whole sample. The remaining psychiatric hospitalization, for postpartum depression, was reported by MDFH02, who also reported early illness onset and Risk-Taking/Irritability score of > 3 . Finally, the possible BD sample ($n = 3/6$) also reported the only BDI-II scores in the severe depression range, which aligns with evidence-based findings of more severe depression in BD. Considering the prevalence of these evidence-based clinical correlations, it is possible that this sample of patients had bipolar depression.

BD Subtype Assessment. While it is not possible to confirm subtype based on these findings, it is possible to infer BD-I or II based on certain factors. Positive BD family history is a clear indicator of increased heritability for both subtypes, but more so for type I. Arguably, a BD-I is more readily identifiable due to significant elated phases and psychotic features like delusions of grandeur, so these two participants would be more at-risk for BD-I. While the three possible BD participants had early onset, MDFH02 reported onset was at 25 years old, on the later end of early, so to speak, after an episode of postpartum depression—nevertheless, closely associated with the onset of BD. While

this depressive episode led to psychiatric hospitalization, both BDFH01 and BDFH06 were hospitalized for overtly high-risk behaviors: BDFH01 for a suicide attempt, BDFH06 for an episode of aggression, both of which are more closely associated with BD-I. While suicidality can certainly occur in the context of BD-II or MDD (and in fact, a recent meta-analysis by Scott et al. did not find a “familial effect” between BD and suicidality), BDFH01 also reported one of the two only significant HCL-32 total scores (the other reported by BDFH06), while MDFH02 did not. The nature of their clinical presentations suggests that both BDFH01 and BDFH06 may have possible BD-I, while MDFH02 may have BD-II. Likewise, the scoring pattern of positive HCL-32 Total and Irritability/Risk-Taking scores may be most indicative of BD-I, while a positive Irritability/Risk-Taking-only may be more suggestive of BD-II.

Study Limitations

Small sample size is one of this study’s main limitations. While larger sample sizes allow for more generalizability, this study aimed to apply “what is known” to identify BD in a small clinical sample, more likely to reflect “real life” situations like small therapy groups or patient types which may be found in non-psychiatric settings and who would benefit from more accurate interventions. Though both mood disorders share the depression factor, patients with bipolar disorder have distinct concerns which warrant more specialized interventions. Thus, patients who are less responsive to traditional MDD treatments might in fact be presenting bipolar depression. As such, a brief battery of screening instruments targeting hypomania, depression and functional assessment, interpreted within these evidence-based clinical correlate considerations, can significantly clarify BD status and potential treatment shifts for optimal outcomes.

Cut-off scores for the HCL-32 and the FAST were extracted from the literature. While these have been well-researched, with good validity and reliability, these instruments have not been validated for Puerto Rican populations. Considering how useful the HCL-32 was in screening for potential BD in this sample, future studies should aim to standardize and validate both the HCL-32 and the FAST for Puerto Ricans with and without mood disorders.

CONCLUSION

BD is a complex mental illness: It takes approximately 10 years to reach an accurate diagnosis, which can limit treatment effectiveness. Evidence-based clinical correlates like BD family history, which point to heritability, have been found to be strong predictors of BD in patients with depression. However, in the absence of BD family history, other correlates like age of onset, reward sensitivity, past substance use, depression severity and functional impairment can suggest a possible BD-II, characterized by predominantly

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depressive or irritable/risk-taking moods. While the body of evidence for MDD/BD-II differential diagnosis is well-established, the current study sought to assess the “real-time” presentation of possible BD in a small clinical sample of $n = 6$ adult Puerto Rican female patients with MDD. Participants were screened for BD with the HCL-32, YMRS, BDI-II, PHQ-9 and FAST. Nonparametric measures were used to assess differences between BD-MDD family history and early-late age of onset groups. Findings were then used to assess possible BD in patients who reported clinically significant scores in HCL-32 ($n = 3$). Findings suggest that early age of onset ($= / < 25$ years) may be a more reliable predictor than BD family history of possible BD in a small clinical sample. However, BD family history was associated with significant BDI-II “loss of pleasure” and “irritability” ratings, both of which are associated with reward sensitivity and risk-taking in BD, supporting the idea of heritability of neuroanatomical correlates like increased BAS system activation. Participants with BD family history tended to score higher across all measures and scored significantly on both HCL-32 total scores and Irritability/Risk-Taking, suggesting possible BD-I in the context of their clinical history, while one participant with MDD family history scored significantly on the Irritability/Risk-Taking scale only, suggesting possible BD-II. Results suggest that the HCL-32 is an effective screening measure with an overall cut-off score of 7 and an I/R-T score of 3. Taken together, age of illness onset, family history, BDI-II severity and positive endorsements of BDI-II irritability and loss of pleasure scores can point to possible BD in patients diagnosed with MDD or with mixed mood presentations.

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